

functionalisation

Manufacturing a sensorised composites glider for structural monitoring

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This article describes how a 1:5 scale glider (SZD-55-1 Nexus) was manufactured using carbon/epoxy material sensorised with Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors to enable enhanced structural monitoring. The work was carried out at Sapienza University of Rome, in the Aerospace Composite Material Lab, under the supervision of Professor Luca Lampani.

To manufacture the glider, the process includes mould manufacturing and treatment, fabrication of fuselage, wing and vertical-horizontal tail skins, as well as prepreg plates to obtain ribs for the wing, tail and frames for fuselage, in addition to fibre optic line installation and final assembly. For the parts, several techniques were used, such as Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI), wet hand lay-up, oven and prepreg plus autoclave. To maintain connection of all parts, modifications were necessary over the course of the project, in particular in the area between the horizontal-vertical stabiliser and the fuselage-wing connection. The material used for the skin was a twill carbon fabric and epoxy resin that can be cured at a low temperature, due to the reduced size of the available autoclave. For the ribs and fuselage frames, a twill carbon fabric prepreg was preferred. The orientation and number of plies is respectively 0° and 3° , a choice that is the result of a static and failure analysis. An optimisation, based on a genetic algorithm, was performed to find the best sensor positions and orientations for modal acquisition. One semi-wing and half fuselage were sensorised for a total of 30 FBGs.

Moulds and treatments

The mould design was drawn using Catia V5 CAD software. When drawing the sketch, the idea was to promote extraction of the composite and visualisation of the areas to be trimmed. Studies of Computerised Numerical Control (CNC) (Figure 2, Shapeoko 3 XXL), milling theory and CAM software (VisualMILL, Fusion 360) were prerequisites for obtaining moulds with the best dimensional accuracy, a high-quality surface finish, and the ability to produce a correct chip. A code was written in Wolfram Mathematica to define

the correct milling parameters based on the machine limits, end mill characteristics and operations. Defining the products to be used on the moulds was critical to eliminating all impurities and pores into which the resin could penetrate and hinder extraction. At the beginning of the project, the squaring, the wasteboard surfacing and the CNC router tramming were checked. Because chips can clog the belt of the CNC, a custom suction system was built from wooden parts with brushes and a tube connecting it to a vacuum cleaner (Figure 2, suction system).

Fig. 1: Horizontal stabiliser skin mould

Fig. 2: Wing skin mould, pocket clearing roughing operation

The dimensions of the polyurethane foam moulds measure 1500 x 500 x 50 mm for the wing skin and 1500 x 650 x 75 mm for the fuselage-vertical tail skin. Because the CNC cutting area is about 838 x 838 mm, the stock materials were cut into two parts using a circular saw along the length (at 750 mm) in order to position them on the bed. For the horizontal stabiliser skin, a piece of purlblock waste measuring 750 x 500 x 28 mm was used (Figure 1). The first step was to square the purlblock sides through a profiling operation (flat endmill), which creates a perfect connection between the two parts of a mould when linked. Then, four operations follow. Pocket clearing roughing (flat endmill) leaves a 1 mm thickness to the final part. Parallel finishing (ball endmill) produces the final dimension of the part along the chord direction of profile. Ramp finishing (ball endmill) serves to define the area that the preceding operation could not reach. Pencil finishing (flat endmill) traces a one-millimetre-thick area to display the end of the composite for trimming operations. Draft angle and S curves are implemented to aid extraction. The minimum radius analysis of Fusion 360 makes it possible to verify whether the endmill has pressed all the areas, leaving the material with the specified thickness. For wing and fuselage moulds (Figure 2, 3), an additional adaptive roughing operation is implemented to produce rectangular holes for connecting the root and tip wing moulds. This operation uses the same endmill and parameters as the pocket clearing.

With respect to the fuselage-vertical skin, a piece of about 150 mm was bonded with epoxy resin to obtain a raw material of 1500 x 650 x 75 mm (Figure 3).

Fig. 3: Fuselage-and vertical tail moulds

On the sides, rectangular pockets (pocket clearing) were created to clamp the mould to the machine bed and to avoid any obstacles over the upper surface stock. After this step, the fuselage and wing mould parts were assembled with two steel plates and 3 C-shape bars of aluminium using screws. Next step was the moulds treatment. First, Sintolit putty was used

to fill the holes between two connected parts and 500-grit sandpaper to remove all asperities. The moulds were washed with water, then dried to eliminate residue. The two last steps can be repeated if necessary. After that, 1000-grit sandpaper was used, a washing and drying step is done if necessary, and all sharp edges were trimmed with a rasp to avoid vacuum bag holes. One coat of Zyvac® surface cleaner was applied with clean cloths to remove contaminants. Nine coats of Chemlease® MPP 712 EZ were applied at thirty-minute intervals. To seal pores, we used 2000-grit sandpaper and five coats of Zyvac® Flex-Z, followed by a release agent every 15 minutes.

Composites parts

The Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) technique (Figure 4) was used to produce the horizontal stabilisers. Once the layers had been applied, a resin pot was connected to an inlet tube and the vacuum pump was placed on the outlet tube. When the resin was released, inlet and outlet tubes were clamped and polymerisation was activated at room temperature. Polymerisation completes in about 4 days.

Fig. 4: Cutting fabric and horizontal tail composite parts production (Liquid Resin Infusion)

Fig. 5: Hand lay-up of wing and fuselage skin, oven, ribs and frames.

Fig. 6: Placement of the FBG line

The wet hand lay-up technique (Figure 5) was selected to produce the wings and fuselage-vertical tail skin after the LRI technique failed due to a bad batch of resin. To support polymerisation, a simple oven capable of maintaining a 60°C temperature was built (Figure 5). To ensure dimensional stability, the temperature must remain below 80°C, which is the maximum admissible temperature for the moulds. For the ribs and frames, 4 composite plates (Figure 5) were created, using the prepreg and autoclave technique, then milled. Holes were drilled on the plates to fix them to the bed of CNC.

Assembly

The excess composite material (Figure 6) was trimmed with a Dremel and sandpaper. Then, wings, fuselage and horizontal tail were assembled.

Two 6-millimetre tick ribs and 2 holes with nuts were fitted in the junction of the Horizontal tail (HS) and the vertical tail.

To attach them, 2 screws and glue epoxy were used. All HS parts are linked with epoxy resin.

To join the wings, the process began with the internal reinforcement structure assembly made of different sized ribs and carbon tubes inserted into each other. A 6-millimetre rib was also placed at the wing root. Parts were glued with epoxy (Figure 6). The sensor positions and

directions were then marked on the wing skin with printed papers using the unfold process in Catia. The FBGs were placed on the wing, aligned in the direction marked in the previous step and glued in place. It is possible to embed the fibres, but this is not easy, and the probability of failure and loss of sensors is high. At the end of curing, the reinforcement structure was placed in position and glued to the upper wing skin. After polymerisation, the epoxy was placed on the ribs and on the lower wing skin to close the parts together. On the wing root rib, two holes were drilled and nuts are inserted in order to screw the wing to the fuselage. Finally, the sensors tested at the start of the assembly process were tested again to ensure that they worked properly.

The same process is used for the fuselage. A 6-millimetre reinforcement rib was located in the inner fuselage skin, where the wings join, to reinforce this area. In addition, an aluminium block was introduced to connect the primary spars (carbon tubes). A Dremel was used in the end to cut an opening in the left fuselage to insert the instrumentation and connect the interrogator to the FBG fibre optic cable. The opening was blocked at some frames with springs, and all the parts were assembled.

Conclusion

The glider, equipped with accelerometers, was subjected to a vibration test to identify the free natural frequencies. Good agreement was found between the FBGs, accelerometers values and FEM data. □

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Fig. 7: Final prototype